

TEACHING ENGLISH ONLINE: THE ENGLISH PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS PERSPECTIVES

Ma. Careen B. Margate ¹ and Dhan Timothy M. Ibojo ²

¹ *Davao de Oro State College, New Bataan, Compostela Valley, Davao de Oro*

² *Assumption College of Nabunturan, Nabunturan, Compostela Valley, Davao de Oro*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10792179>

ABSTRACT

Teaching practicum equip pre-service teachers in the teaching learning process. Through engaging themselves in teaching in the classroom and receiving of feedback from their mentors, they are able to improve and master their teaching skills necessary in their profession. However, due to the sudden shift of education caused by COVID-19 pandemic, the English pre-service teachers of Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology, Trento External Studies Center (ASSCAT, TSC) conducted their teaching practicum online. Hence, this qualitative phenomenological research study explored the experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms and insights gained of the English pre-service teachers in teaching English online. The findings of this study was also utilized in order to design a suitable intervention program for the existing phenomenon. Phenomenological method of research was utilized with in-depth-interview guide questions which were validated by a panel of validators. The ten English pre-service teachers were purposely selected through a fishbowl method in the conduct of the study. Findings revealed that the English pre-service teachers perceived their experiences as difficult yet fulfilling. The study also revealed that the participants were challenged in their lesson delivery and lesson preparations due to the poor internet connection and unavailability of devices to be used in online teaching. Moreover, their experiences in teaching English online had given them the ideas on the real life of a teacher. Through this insights and experiences gained in teaching online, the English pre-service teachers believed that they were made prepared for their profession. The study ends with recommendations for preparatory programs or trainings for online

teaching, provision on the use of technology and internet signal, and a face-to-face interactions with the cooperating teachers for feedback.

Keywords: *English pre-service teachers, teaching English online, teaching practicum, experiences, coping mechanisms, phenomenology*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching practicum establishes the most essential part of teacher education for it provides pre-service teachers (PST) with hands-on experiences in teaching. For many PSTs, their practicum experiences are the most challenging, difficult, and frustrating period of their program for this is where they experience the teachers' many complex tasks involved in actual classroom practice (Ersin, 2020). Through teaching practicum, PSTs can be equipped in the teaching learning process. Through engaging themselves in teaching and receiving feedback from their mentors, PSTs are able to improve and master their teaching skills (Murray-Harvey et al., 2000).

In March of 2020, however, the unprecedented impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has dramatically changed the educational practices. Because of lockdowns and quarantines, schools were closed which made the distance education ubiquitous. Pre-service teachers in practicum courses had to cease from teaching in schools. The instructors of Marmara University in Turkey shift to uploading of articles for PSTs to read and reflect on or videos taken from different actual classes. They could watch and analyze them in place of the teaching practicum. In these, many PSTs felt "incomplete" and "disappointed" for not being able to engage in macro-teaching to get feedback from their university supervisors and mentors. Many also have reported that they felt unprepared and unready to teach for their future career (Ersin, 2020).

In the Province of Quirino, since the country has the slowest and most expensive internet setup (Fabito et al. 2020 and Yra et al. 2020), this stresses the factors affecting the experiences of the PSTs of Quirino State University – Diffun Campus, Quirino Province. As their practicum was done at home using the internet, resources were not enough to produce instructional materials which impedes their productivity and performance. This resulted in the feeling that something was missing, describing their experiences as insufficient since they did not experience the rigor of the actual student teaching. Moreover, their experiences do not necessarily boost or develop the confidence needed in the field (Laguitao et al. 2021).

In Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology, Trento Satellite Campus (ASSCAT, TSC), the PSTs under the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) major in English program also share the same problem. Due to the temporary closures of schools, PSTs were deployed inside the ASSCAT Trento campus where the BSED instructors became their cooperating teachers (CT). However, since there are only four BSED teachers in ASSCAT Trento campus, the 42 BSED-English PSTs were divided into four to be accommodated. The PSTs were given topics to teach online and will be given feedback from their CT after. However, PSTs were only given a few online teaching experiences because of the number of PST per CT. The problem with the internet strength as well as the availability of personal computers, mobile phones and the like had also been their challenges as they have to conduct their classes online too.

They were not given the chance as well to craft their own instructional materials or record students' progress through quizzes and exams and even live interaction with the learners which the researcher considers a great problem since the teaching practicum should be preparing the PSTs in their real job in the future.

Since the teaching practicum is an essential part of every PST's course program, it is therefore necessary to identify what are the experiences and problems being encountered by them in this new system of teaching practicum. Moreover, the researcher would also like to identify how else the school, the administrator, the instructors and the mentors can extend help and support for the preparedness of these prospective teachers. By this, the result of this study might become the basis for intervention like seminars, trainings or programs that might further help the future PSTs in their preparedness in teaching English online.

Research Questions

1. What are the experiences of the English pre-service teachers in teaching English online?

- 1.1. How do you describe your experience as a pre-service teacher in teaching English online?
- 1.2. What preparations did you do in teaching English online?
- 1.3. What programs in college prepare you for teaching English online?

2. What challenges do the English pre-service teachers encounter during teaching English online?

- 2.1. What difficulties have you encountered in the teaching and learning process of English subjects online?
- 2.2. What English lessons do you find difficult to teach online?
- 2.3. What were the challenges you encountered with technology in the delivery of English lessons during online teaching?
- 2.4. What were the causes of each of the challenges you encountered during teaching English online?

3. How do the English pre-service teachers cope with the challenges encountered in teaching English online?

- 3.1. What were the mechanisms you utilized to cope with the challenges you encountered in teaching English online?
- 3.2. How did you teach difficult English lessons online?
- 3.3. How did you deal with the difficulties on the use of technology in teaching English online?
- 3.4. What assistance were given to you by the school, the administration, and the cooperating teachers?

4. What are the insights gained by the English pre-service teachers during teaching English online?

- 4.1. What are the insights you gained with your experience in teaching English online?

4.2. In your own perspective as a pre-service teacher, what are needed to be considered during the implementation of online teaching?

4.3. What assistance should be provided to pre-service teachers that may help them to prepare for their professional life by the school, the administrator and the cooperating teachers?

4.4. How did your experiences in teaching English online prepare you in your teaching profession?

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in Trento, Agusan del Sur. This only focused on the experiences, challenges and coping mechanisms of the Bachelor of Secondary Education pre-service teachers of Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology, Trento Satellite Campus (ASSCAT, TSC). However, this study was limited only on the ten (10) major in English pre-service teachers who were officially enrolled during the first semester of school year 2021-2022, specifically in their teaching internship between May - June, 2022. The duration was good enough to get in touch and scheduled an interview with the English pre-service teachers.

This study used phenomenological research design since the issue that was explored through this study were the experiences of the English pre-service teachers during their English online practicum, their challenges and the mechanisms they had utilized in order to cope with their challenges. The researcher adopted the concept of Creswell (2013) who stated that the ideal number of participants in a phenomenological research ranges from 5 – 25 participants. The participants were chosen using Purposive Sampling through fishbowl method. It is a non-probability sampling method and it occurs when “elements selected for the sample are chosen by the judgment of the researcher. Researchers often believe that they can obtain a representative sample by using a sound judgment, which will result in saving time and money (Black, 2010).

In the process of collecting data for this research, an In-depth Interview (IDI) was conducted to the English pre-service teachers of Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology, Trento Satellite Campus (ASSCAT, TSC). IDI is done to avoid the possibility of misinterpretation (Creswell, 2008). The researcher used audio recorder and video recorder so as to make it valid and reliable. The validity and reliability of the collected data played a significant role in the study. It was very important to foster trust and confidence in collecting of data among the participants in order to get the truth and honest response from them. In-depth interview was employed in data collection in which participants were interviewed individually in their most convenient time, place, and manner.

The researcher used her prepared open-ended questions. This gave the informant the opportunity to express freely his/her thoughts and views as it is very significant to the success of the study. The audio and video recorders were used to obtain a precise and accurate data (Boyce and Neale, 2006).

With the use of audio and video recorder, the researcher documented the qualitative responses of the English pre-service teachers during the interview which consisted of the additional comments of all the participants, making the research

questions as the instrument. The researcher then transcribed, noted down information, analyzed, validated, and schematized the content of the data.

Analysis began after the data collection period. The collected data were reviewed, synthesized, and documented in order to keep careful and detailed notes. This was very important due the short time frame for data collection. After the completion of the formal data collection period, analysis began. The qualitative data were analyzed and examined collectively to provide a holistic picture. All the data collected were transcribed and analyzed according to the research questions.

RESULTS

1. What are the experiences of the English pre-service teachers in teaching English online?

Description of Experience as Pre-service Teaching English Online	Considerably Difficult
	Struggling
	Fulfilling
	Stressful
	A Different Experience Compared to Face-to-Face
	Delighted to Teach
	Tense Feeling but Exciting
	Challenging
Preparations Made in Teaching English Online	Self-Preparation
	Preparation of Learning Materials
	Ensure Better Internet Connection
College Programs that Help Pre-service Teachers in Teaching English Online	Get Some Learning from Demo Teaching
	Get Some Learning From Subjec
	Get Some Learning From Instructors
	Nothing at All

2. What challenges do the English pre-service teachers encounter during teaching English Online?

Difficulties Encountered in the Teaching and Learning Process	Problem with Internet Connectivity
	Difficulty with the Delivery of Subject Online
	Problem with Students' Learning
	Problem with the Preparation
	Lesson preparations
	Familiarity with English Language
Difficult English Lessons to Teach Online	Subject-Verb Agreement
	Vocabulary
	Proper Pronunciation
	Lessons in Literature
	No Lessons were Found Difficult to Teach
Challenges Encountered with	Literacy on the Use of Technology
	Poor Internet Connection

Technology in the Delivery of English Lessons	Challenges in Looking for Online Resources
	Cheating in the Internet
	Malfunctioning Laptop
Causes of the Challenges Encountered	Poor Internet Connection
	Being Unfamiliar with Word Meaning
	Curriculum Still New
	Lack of Budget for Internet Connection
	Improper Delivery of Lessons
	Unprepared for the Pandemic
Being New to Online Modality	

3. How do the English pre-service teachers cope with the challenges encountered in teaching English online?

Mechanisms Utilized to Cope with Challenges Encountered	Study Lessons First
	Be Determined in Delivering the Lesson
	Need for Gadgets and Internet Connection
	Develop Learning Materials
	Search for Word Meaning
	Engage Students at the Start of Session
	Use of Interactive Platform
	Ways Used to Teach Difficult English Lessons
	Find Ways to Simplify Lessons
	Do Research in the Internet
Ways Used in Dealing with Difficulties on the Use of Technology	Tried to be Adaptable
	Make Use of What's Available
	Reach out to Peers
	Do Self-exploration
	Tried to Endure Amid the Limitation
	Deal Squarely Any Challenge at Hand
Assistance from School, Administration and Cooperating Teachers	Guidance from Cooperating Teacher
	Getting Techniques from Cooperating Teacher
	Getting Personal Help from Administration and Cooperating Teachers
	Flexibility of School and Administration
	Administration Provided Classrooms
	School as Venue for Learning
	Scholarship from School
	Getting Support from Administration for Online Teaching
Free Internet Connection from School	

4. What are the Insights Gained by the English Pre-Service Teachers in Teaching English Online?

Insights Gained with Experience in Teaching English Online	It Pays to be a Good Intern
	Online Teaching is Really Challenging
	Be an Open-minded Teacher
	Teaching not an Easy Profession
	Good Preparation Works

Things Needed during the Implementation of Online Teaching	Find Ways to Connect to Students Online
	Preparation of Lessons
	Consider the Learning of the Child
Assistance to be Provided from the School, the Administrator and the Cooperating Teachers to Pre-service Teachers for Professional Life	Training for Teaching Strategies
	Provision for Internet Connection
	Introduce More Challenging Tasks
	Cooperating Teacher as Role Model
	Guidance from Cooperating Teacher
	Cooperating Teachers Gave all the Support
Ways that the Experiences in Teaching English Online Prepare the Pre-service Teachers for their Teaching Profession	Get Some Ideas on Teaching
	Learned About the Life of a Teacher
	Learned Some Strategies and Approaches
	Able to Build Confidence to Face Students

DISCUSSION

The structured themes and the emerging themes were made as foundation in broadening the discussion of the findings in this study. As each theme was linked to related literature and studies, a substantial discussion was made to find their alignment with the theme.

Description of Experience as Pre-service Teaching English Online. The emerging themes in this structured theme are considerably difficult, struggling, fulfilling, stressful, a different experience compared to face to face, delighted to teach, tense feeling but exciting, and challenging. These were the definition of the English pre-service teachers on their experience in teaching English online.

The findings revealed that considerably difficult is the commonly used definition of the pre-service teacher participants in their experiences in teaching English online, which can also be interrelated with the definition challenging, struggling and stressful. Most of the participants found their experiences as these due to the sudden shift of learning modality which left them and the institution unprepared in their program. Moreover, due to the scarcity of materials and resources used for online teaching, the pre-service teachers consider it hard to teach their lessons online.

Meanwhile, it was also found out that the pre-service teachers experienced fulfillment in their internship experiences, delight and excitement in teaching English online. Though the experience was new and different compared to face to face which they preferred more, still, they were able to learn and adjust in order for them achieve to the tasks given to them as pre-service teachers.

As pre-service teachers, teaching online as result to the pandemic is difficult. In the study of the Secret Teachers (2020), most pre-service teachers find it difficult, some thrived, and some sunk due to the quick and unprepared shift to online teaching. Thus, the situation evolves more which gave pre-service teachers with little help or guidance during their teaching practicum.

Barnesa, Hall, Lower, Pottinger and Popham (2020) also revealed that amidst the pandemic, pre-service teachers who were teaching at private colleges were struggling with little assistance and even training from their teacher education programs.

They did not receive consistent and thorough feedback from their cooperating teachers or program mentors. Some of them were also left behind, unable to adequately address their worries about what to teach and what not to teach, as well as how to educate and assess.

To teach online is also challenging as the pre-service teachers perceive it. Laguitao, Cubalit, Teppang, dela Cruz and Bautista (2021) claimed that online learning is challenging as to some factors that need to be considered such as the connectivity, area, and of course, the monetary consideration or financial capability of both the teachers and the learners. Correspondingly, it has also become stressful since online teaching-learning in pandemic was a new experience for teachers, pre-service teachers and students to be involved in (Mishraa, Gupta, Shree, 2020).

Furthermore, the pre-service also considered their practicum experience as a different experience from face-to-face. Koşar (2021) appealed that the online or distance education embodied a number of disadvantages including the absence of effective communication, which is the one that takes place in face-to-face classes. Consequently, this leads to the difficulty of the mentors to be faced by students as well as the deficiency to socialize with them.

The pre-service teachers also described their experience as tensed but exciting. In fact, in the study of Cooper, Warren, Hogan-Chapman and Mills (2020), the pre-service teachers who experienced creating and instructing an online module felt comfortable with adjusting for different learning styles, using a variety of assessments, facilitating student responsibility for learning, providing an alternative explanation or example when students seemed to be confused, responding to defiant students online, facilitating collaborative learning, and providing effective learning experiences for students, as well as appropriate challenges for the very capable. These experiences caused them fulfillment as they were able to do tasks of a real teacher. Pre-service teachers reported their satisfaction in learning and teaching from their practicum experiences, which reinforces their personal and professional development (Kaldi, 2009).

Preparations Made in Teaching English Online. The preparations made by the English pre-service teachers in teaching English online were self-preparation, preparation of learning materials and ensuring better internet connection.

Based on the findings, the English pre-service teachers made self-preparation in terms of lesson planning and delivery before they got themselves in the learning process. Also, since online learning is a learning that takes place in the internet, another preparation they did was their learning materials which include their instructional materials like PowerPoint presentations. Also, mobile phone, laptop or personal computer were also being readied. More importantly, the English pre-service ensured their internet connectivity.

The findings revealed that self-preparation is the most common preparation done by the participants. As stated by Mercado (2008), to make online learning possible necessitates teacher's perceived readiness in terms of preparation and implementation. Additionally, online learning programs must include a methodical planning approach, as well as designing and implementing a student-friendly learning environment.

Also, when it comes to learning materials, formulating a lesson plan has been one of the preparation made by the participants. This result braced the study of Laguitao *et.al.* (2021) which claimed that lesson planning has been always the plight of pre-service teaching for it is one of the major concerns when it comes to evaluating the competencies and preview of the over-all outcomes. Since it is the blueprint of the learning process, it has to be done cautiously. Additionally, pre-service teachers were also required to plan, monitor, and control their learning processes more autonomously in order to follow self-study materials, organize participation in asynchronous and synchronous events (Naujoks et al., 2021).

Another material that the pre-service teacher prepared are their resources. Though they do not have enough resources due to the pandemic, thus they still look for ways for them to find one. It buoyed the same study of Laguitao *et.al.* (2021) who found that because their practicum is done at their comfort zones, resources are not enough for them to produce instructional materials and other needs for learning such as printers, speakers, and others. Strengthening the study of Hadijah and Shalawati (2021) which said that the pre-service teachers did not have rich resources for their teaching, so the information in the learning media just refer to very limited content to practice the language.

Additionally, Febrianto, Mas'udah and Megasari (2020) noted that the teacher also needs to prepare online learning materials comprehensively to cover the requirements of the syllabus and show them through the integration of technology. Since preparing online learning materials is not a simple task to do, the pre-service and in-service teachers need to train themselves for that purpose (Hadajih and Shalawati, 2021).

Ensuring a better internet signal is another main preparation to do since the internet is the bloodline in the new normal of education (Laguitao *et.al.*, 2021). It supported the study of Ardiyansah (2021) who stated that both teachers and students must prepare such devices to support the process in carrying out online learning. Several types of equipment such as personal computers, smartphones, and internet connections are required to facilitate this process.

College Programs that Help Pre-service Student in Teaching English Online.

Based on the findings of this study, the participants in this study received help in teaching English online through college programs given to them. They get some learning from demo teaching, get some learning from subject, get some learning from instructors and nothing at all.

Learning from subject and instructors is one way that the pre-service teachers in this study were being helped. They were helped not by any form of program nor trainings but by their teaching process. It supported the study of Hadijah and Shalawati (2021) who expressed that the teacher-educators have essential roles in guiding the pre-service teachers and in-service teachers to perform their teaching interestingly, effectively, and innovatively. It backed the study of Ardiyansah (2021) which claimed that despite the experiences in teaching online, some pre-service teachers who did not have the experiences were still confident because they were exposed to online learning from the university before joining the internship program. Most of them reflect on what their lecturers have taught them in online

learning and use it in teaching online in the internship program. Moreover, his study revealed that pre-service teachers had gained experience in online learning during their learning process in the university.

With honesty, some of the participants in this study answered that there was no specific college program given to them as pre-service teachers. This supported the study of Zawacki-Richter (2020) which said that many initial teacher education programs were not fully prepared for online instruction by the start of the summer 2020. Which is why in contrast to plan and well-design online learning environments, emergency remote teaching during COVID-19 has become the fast, temporary shift of instruction to an alternate delivery mode (Hodges et al., 2020).

Difficulties Encountered in the Teaching and Learning Process. The emerging themes in this structured theme are problem with the internet connectivity, difficulty with the delivery of subject online, problem with students' learning, problem with the preparation, lesson preparations and familiarity with English language.

In teaching English online, the English pre-service teachers encountered various challenges which caught up the learning process of the students. As the internet connection in the Philippines was poor, the most common problem the participants experienced was their connectivity to the internet. In effect, it links to the problem in the delivery of their lesson to their lessons due to lagging and losing of connection. Also, another problem which pertains to the learning of the students had emerged. Moreover, due to the number of tasks the pre-service teachers had to do, the problem with the preparation of materials and lesson plans had also occurred. Likewise, it was found out that the participants encountered problem with the familiarity of the language.

Internet connectivity was the first problem encountered by the English pre-service teachers in teaching online. It is one of the main problems that usually occur in online learning, such as the unavailability of devices and internet connection issues. Supporting the study of Efriana (2021) who mentioned that students' issues in online learning are in the form of inactivity in following learning, limited supporting facilities, and internet network access. It was also found out in the study of Agung and Surtikanti (2020) that the students are also struggling to follow the online learning systems because of some factors including the availability and sustainability of the internet connection.

Difficulty with the delivery of subject online was another challenge that the pre-service teachers encountered in their teaching practicum. As stated by Popova and Pikulenko (2020), the pre-service teachers need to advance their skills in engaging the students during online learning. Because the pre-service teachers have not fully understood how to engage the students, engagement became one of the issues. This issue was found because the pre-service teachers were busy on elucidating the content in the PowerPoint slides that they had prepared. Thus, this supports the study of Atmojo and Nugroho (2020) when they revealed that the interaction among the pre-service teachers and other students rarely happen during the online practice. Furthermore, the pre-service teachers did not show cheerfulness and fervor in their learning because they looked frightened and had flat intonation when clarifying the lesson to the students (Zayapragassarazan, 2020).

Problem with students' learning was the result of the delayed communication which is one weakness of online learning that is reported by many researchers. According to the study by Howland and Moore (2002), the communication between students and between students and instructor was a serious issue. The absence of face-to-face interaction between student and instructor contributed to undesirable perceptions of many students. Students felt apprehensive in guidance when the feedback from instructor was delayed. In addition, they also found that many students reported that it was difficult to get clarification on assignments, etc. due to lack of communication between student and instructor. The general impression of communication between students was also negative. Correspondingly, Petride's (2002) also reported that some participants felt a lack of immediacy in responses in the online context in comparison to what could typically occur in a structured face-to-face class discussion. This appears to be especially obvious in asynchronous online discussions, when students have to wait for others to read and respond back to their postings or e-mail messages. Lack of a sense of online community and the feelings of isolation were other weakness that learners have reported in their online learning experiences. Vonderwell (2003) reported that online learning participants indicated a lack of connection with the instructor, especially "one-on-one" relationship with the instructor.

Problem with the preparation is another challenge that the pre-service teachers encountered in teaching online. Thus, all of the issues experienced by the pre-service teachers are core elements that can affect the quality of the teaching if they are not well prepared. Popova and Pikulenko (2020) affirmed that by preparing for performing online teaching can be an effective way to present online learning. In a previous study conducted by Atmojo and Nugroho (2020), they found that a group of English teachers did not run their online teaching effectively because of lack of preparation and planning to teach online. Therefore, teachers must acquire how to prepare and run online teaching effectively (Zayapragassarazan, 2020). They have to be resourceful to find out the best ways that they can take to improve their skills in teaching online.

An old saying says that when you fail to plan, you plan to fail. Which is why, Dizon (2021) insisted that in teaching, lesson planning should be carried out properly and effectively. This emphasizes the statements that lesson planning is hard for them especially on creating, revising, and preparing instruction. Moreover, the time frame during their submission to their cooperating teacher for improvement and editing is another factor. In addition, financial limit was also seen as a factor on their instructional material construction as some of them are financially instable.

Lastly, the English pre-service teachers encountered unfamiliarity with English language to be used in teaching. In the study of Hadijah and Shalawatih (2021), they recommended that the pre-service teachers need to have better communication skills in verbal or written communication modes. The explanation and instruction have to be given clearly to avoid misunderstanding, especially in giving of tasks. The pre-service and in-service teachers need to be guided to deliver the information in simple manners, such as using high-frequency words, simple sentence constructions, and clear pronunciation. Thus, opening extra communication channels can be a solution to help the students in getting clear information and avoiding misunderstanding and demotivating in their learning activities.

Furthermore, to be an English teacher, a person should have a good command of English. Meaning, the language should be comprehensible, intelligible and understandable to receivers (Gallaway and Rose, 2015; Jenkins, 2014).

Difficult English Lessons to Teach Online. The emerging themes in this structured theme are subject-verb agreement, vocabulary, lessons in literature, proper pronunciation and no lessons were found difficult to teach.

In teaching English online, the pre-service teachers found some English lessons that are hard to be taught via online. Subject-Verb Agreement (SVA) was the most common of all these lessons. Vocabulary learning is also a challenge for them as well as pronunciation. Few participants also raised difficulty in teaching literatures to their students.

Subject-Verb Agreement or grammar rules is the central component of language (Greenbourn, 2002). Grammar is rules for forming words and making sentences. It means that grammar is the central component of language, which consists of rules of grammatical structure. Teaching grammar is one of the challenges that every English teacher encounter. The findings of the study conducted by Halim, Wahid and Halim (2021) showed that teachers and students face more challenges in online grammar classes than the traditional classes. The problems occur when teachers try to give while students receive instructions online. In face-to-face classes, teachers can demonstrate examples on the spot. Moreover, some learners feel confident when they can see the teachers in front of them. Their tone, facial expressions, body language all contribute to the learning process.

On the other hand, vocabulary knowledge is one of the foundations of understanding students' literacy, as well as, determining teachers teaching performance (Muhamad and Kiely, 2018). Teaching them is a challenge especially when a teacher has but a few vocabulary only. Apparent to the study of Ocampo and McNeill (2019), teachers' ability to use and teach English confidently and fluently in the classroom depends on how much vocabulary they know. Vocabulary size is not only imperative on teachers' ability to engage in natural communication but also to other learning abilities such as listening, reading and writing skills. Teachers' vocabulary knowledge is important as they normally are responsible in giving correct feedback on words that students might not understand (Deocampo, 2020).

English Literature or literature in general is a diverse field and different forms of literary texts have their own peculiarities where the learners need to approach the text differently (Savvidou, 2004). Teaching literature requires exploration to several genres. This means that one's involvement in the lecture is a crucial factor in its teaching and learning process (Van, 2009). Such difficulty in teaching literature is affirmed by Islam (2021) who said that in an online class, teaching this diverse field can get difficult for the instructor as certain genres require special setting and active involvement from the students in the lesson. Because reading literature requires different approaches from the teacher as well as the learner.

Meanwhile, pronunciation is often regarded as the Cinderella of language education. Good pronunciation is regarded as a desirable quality in language teachers and a lack of it can cause criticism and questioning of professional identity (Eksi and

Yeşilçınar, 2015). However, pronunciation instruction seems to have received less attention than other fields in Second Language Acquisition (SLA) (Derwing and Munro, 2005)

Challenges Encountered with Technology in the Delivery of English Lessons. The emerging themes in this structured theme are literacy on the use of technology, poor internet connection, challenges in looking for online resources, cheating in the internet and malfunctioning laptop.

The pre-service teachers also encountered challenges regarding technology during their online practicum. As emerged, literacy on the use of technology pertains to the pre-service knowledge on the how of the technology in teaching online. Poor internet connection is also present which brings also the challenges on looking for online resources to be used in their lesson. Also, cheating in the internet as well as malfunctioning laptop had emerged.

Literacy on the use of technology was one of the difficulty of the pre-service teachers. Because online learning in the participant's school is just new, there was no enough program and training given to them. Although today's pre-service teachers commonly use ICT applications in their daily lives, the use of such apps for teaching and learning purposes is more problematic (Sailer *et al.*, 2021). One possible reason is that pre-service teachers themselves have limited personal experience of digital learning environments (Valtonen *et al.*, 2015). Despite their familiarity with various ICT applications, pre-service teachers show limited skills in utilizing these in teaching and learning (Valtonen *et al.*, 2011), highlighting the need for initial teacher education programs to address the current deficit (Martin, 2015). Of particular importance is pre-service teachers' motivation to integrate technology into classroom practice (Backfisch *et al.*, 2021).

On the other hand, internet connection is the greatest factor affecting the teaching and learning process. In the study of Laguitao *et.al.* (2021), some places have weaker connection or some do not have any connection at all, but generally internet connection in the country is expensive. This supports Ardiyansah (2020) as he claimed that the pre-service teachers were also concerned about the technical issues from the students since most of the students were located in remote areas with limited internet connection and unavailability devices.

In the result of the study of Laguitao *et.al* (2021), it was found out that the lack of resources impedes productivity of the pre-service teachers. Adapting to online teaching, pre-service teachers face significant challenges in maintaining development and supporting the learners' needs. Since their practicum is done at their homes, resources are not enough to produce instructional materials and other needs for learning such as printers, speakers, and others. Unlike the traditional classes, the needs of pre-service teachers are already given in terms of a classroom, laboratory materials, supplies, and equipment, and other instructional materials readily for use. However, in new normal, it is then where they need to be creative and resourceful in terms of their needs

Meanwhile, in the online environment, cheating extends beyond signaling and exchanging answers. Moten, Fitterer, Brazier, Leonard, and Brown (2013) detailed some options of online cheating that included students waiting for their classmates to get the answers. Their study pointed out that when students take their exams in a non-

proctored environment, they may also use multiple computers to facilitate cheating. On one computer, they will have the exam open, while the others provide Internet access, which is used to browse for answers. Even in Florida, cheating had happened which had made national headlines in 2007 when almost two dozen athletes at Florida State University were caught cheating in their online classes (Kaczor, 2007).

Gadgets and devices are number one factor also in learning online. In the Philippines, several studies showed some contrasting sentiments with regards to internet connectivity and the use of gadgets or devices for online learning. In a study by Fabito et al., (2020) the group revealed that one of the barriers and challenges in online learning is that poor students do not own laptops and desktop computers and have limited internet connections which concept relates to the study of Cleofas and Rocha (2021). Another study showed that the greater number of device types owned by a student, the greater the level of learning readiness they have (Estira, 2020). In addition, from another state university in the country, a study revealed the students' readiness for online classes however, the burden from computer and internet rentals in cafes exists (Yra et al., 2020).

Causes of the Challenges Encountered. The emerging themes in this structured theme are: poor internet connection, being unfamiliar with word meaning, curriculum is still new, lack of budget for internet connection, improper delivery of lessons, unprepared for the pandemic and being new to online modality.

Based on the data collected from the participants of the study, the pre-service teachers consider the poor internet connection as the cause of the difficulties they have encounter in teaching English language. In connection, the lack of budget for internet connection also emerged. Moreover, the unfamiliarity with word meaning and improper delivery of the lessons were also few of the causes. The pre-service teachers also think that the new curriculum was another cause which made them become new to the online modality.

Poor internet connection caused poor access to online platforms. In the study of Coman, Tiru, Schmitz, Stanciu and Bularca (2020), internet connection problems are existing, especially when the number of students connected was high. Even more, the issues on poor internet connection and poor mobile connection has caused low students' participation in the online learning. It was shown that the students' remaining technical problems are poor internet connections, signal loss, lack of adequate digital devices, especially for students living in rural areas or students from families with low incomes.

Because the Philippines is one of the countries offering the slowest and most expensive internet connection in Asia (Fabito *et.al.*, 2020), the pre-service teachers consider their lack of budget for internet connection a cause of their difficulties in teaching English online. It was supported by Demuyakor, J. (2020) who conducted a study on coronavirus (COVID -19) and online learning in higher institutions of education and reported that students encounter challenges during their online teaching and learning due to the high cost of internet data for students who are currently outside China.

Being unfamiliar with word meaning is another cause of the challenges encountered by the pre-service teachers. This backed up the study of Hadijah and

Shalawati (2020) who stressed that the pre-service teachers need use familiar words to have better communication skills in verbal or written communication modes with the students. The explanation and instruction have to be given clearly to avoid misunderstanding, especially in giving tasks to the learners.

Proper delivery of the lesson is another thing to be considered in teaching. Sun et al., in their study on students' experience during online courses showed that students believe that teachers should identify how to adjust their lectures to the online environment and not just to simply transfer online the information that was usually taught in the traditional way, and that they should give satisfactory number of projects and assignments. Backed with the study of Suresh, Priya and Gayathri (2018) involving the 424 universities around the world, it revealed that institutions were affected by the pandemic in terms of education delivery. Most universities stated that they had to adopt online learning and had to face many challenges, and one of the the most important is the teachers' ability to deliver online courses. Thus, in order to continue to properly deliver education, optimization of the E-learning process is necessary.

The sudden shift to online learning due to the pandemic which brings new curriculum was also consider the cause of the difficulties that the pre-service teachers have encountered in teaching English online. Its unprecedented shift also left the teachers and students to be unprepared for online teaching and learning. Laguiato *et.al* (2020) revealed that because the pre-service teachers first experienced distance learning in the heights of the pandemic in 2020, the distance and blended learning including modular approach, the sudden change of the environment in learning and the curriculum and pedagogical reforms has become one of the most common factors of students being unprepared in their endeavor.

Lastly, being new to online modality was also raised as the cause of the challenges of the pre-service teachers in teaching English online. This supported the study of Coman *et.al.* (2020) who revealed that in spite of all problems encountered, students relate problems to the context of the pandemic when both teachers and students were forced to deal with a situation they hadn't faced before. In result, some teachers did try to learn, find solutions, offer support for students and adapt their teaching style to the new conditions, things that some students appreciated despite the existing technical difficulties. Furthermore, the reason why the online educational process encountered so many issues is represented by the fact that the traditional way in which teachers used to deliver the practical part of the course was no longer suitable for the online environment. Thus, because they did not manage to rapidly adapt and come up with solutions, teachers created confusion and uncertainty among students.

Mechanisms Utilized to Cope with the Challenges Encountered. The emerging themes in this structured theme are: study lessons first, determination in delivering the lesson, need for gadgets and internet connection, develop learning materials, search for word meaning, engage students at the start of the session and use of interactive platform.

With the challenges being encountered by the English pre-service teachers in teaching English online, it has been found out that they study their lessons first and do search for word meaning before entering the class. They were also determination to deliver their lessons, developed learning materials and used interactive platforms which

helps the learners be engaged in learning. As to gadgets and internet connection, they made use of these materials for self-exploration in order to cope with the challenges.

Studying the lessons first before teaching them was the most common mechanisms used by the pre-service teachers in coping with their challenges. In the study of Esani (2010), he cited that the time and labor-intensive work for lesson preparation that is required in online course development and delivery are greater than that of regular classroom teaching. Therefore, the instructor must start preparing for an online course long before the course starts. This requires hours in front of a computer screen typing every instruction that could be verbally communicated in a face-to-face setting with minimal effort. This is because every aspect of the course must be carefully organized with explicit and detailed instructions.

Moreover, the determination in the delivery of the lesson was also practiced by the pre-service teachers to cope on the challenges they had in teaching English online. Naah (2020) claimed that the pre-service teachers may be challenged by poor internet access, lesson delivery and assessment challenges, and lack of interest in online lessons however, considering them as college learners, it is also expected that these pre-service teachers can manage their time effectively and develop communication and technological skills. By then, they must be dynamic, exhibit commitment and accept the flexibility that goes with online teaching and learning.

The need for gadgets and internet connection bolstered the study of Baluyos (2021) who claimed that online learning is made possible through an internet connection and functional gadgets. Therefore, it proves that stable internet connection and available technological resources play a vital role in online learning. There is a need for an updated gadget and a stable platform/software for online classes. These may help them especially in synchronous classes.

Meanwhile, to develop comprehensive learning materials to be used in teaching online is always necessary to cover the requirements of the syllabus and show them through the integration of technology (Febrianto, Mas'udah and Megasari, 2020). It supported the study of Baluyos (2021) who claimed that preparation of learning materials is one of the teachers mechanism to for it serve as a supplement for the teacher's instruction. Therefore, the preparation of learning materials is a prerequisite to online teaching. They feel the need to prepare the learning materials first, especially the PowerPoint presentations needed to be presented to the students before online classes.

Searching for word meaning is another factor which the pre-service teachers consider as help in teaching online. In the study of Nation (2001), he showed that students' first language has an important role in understanding communication context. The students are at ease to understand the context if it is explained using their first language. Moreover, the different mother languages made the pre-service teachers difficult in implementing the learning process, especially in explaining the material online which is why, searching its word meaning and translating it to the mother language became their mechanisms in coping these challenges in vocabulary.

Lastly, engaging the students at the start of the session is another mechanisms used by the pre-service teachers. This is somehow connected to the use of interactive platform in teaching English online. This strengthened the study of Darby (2020) who explained that an online teacher must create a coherent learning experience for students they may not meet face-to-face. In action, they must develop new support

strategies that maintain motivation and encourage interaction in the online classroom. Therefore, Dhawan (2020) attested that online teaching and learning enable educators must customize their procedures and processes based on the needs of the learners. He further explained that there are plenty of online tools available which is important for an effective and efficient teaching and learning processes.

Ways Used to Teach Difficult English Lessons. The emerging themes in this structured theme are: find ways to simplify lessons and do research in the internet. Due to the distance between the pre-service teachers to their cooperating teachers, they had to look for ways in order for them teach the difficult lessons assigned to them. There were two ways that they do; first, they looked for way to simplify the lessons and did research in the internet.

Simplifying the difficult lessons were used by the participants in order for them to teach the difficult lessons they have in English. Mahmoud (2014) stated that linguistic simplification can be clearly distinguished from simplification of learning task, and the various linguistic achievement strategies employed by learners can be seen as bridging steps leading from task simplification to linguistic simplification as one of the outcomes of task simplification. Moreover, he also believed that linguistic simplification is not a strategy, it is the result of the learner's use of various learning and communication strategies. Thus, it could also be a 'teaching' strategy, and not a 'learning' strategy. Thus, caretakers and language teachers simplify the language in order to assure effectiveness in delivery whereas language learners simplify the learning task for effective learning.

The second technique for the pre-service teachers to teach their difficult lesson was to do research. It supported the study of Laguitao *et.al* (2021) where the pre-service teachers claimed that internet is their hero in this pandemic. For this reason, although they are burdened in having internet for their studies, they still need to secure a good internet connection. The study of Pastores, Dacanay, Mayoya, Nanglihan, and Bautista (2021) claimed that students in this pandemic are mostly internet dependent as teachers are seemed to be absent. Moreover, the informants claimed further that Mr. Google seems to be their teacher in this pandemic.

Ways Used in Dealing with Difficulties on the Use of Technology. The emerging themes in this structured theme are: tried to be adaptable, make use of what's available, reach out to peers, do self-exploration, tried to endure amid the limitation and deal squarely any challenge at hand.

The pre-service teachers amidst their difficulties had many ways in dealing their difficulties on the use of technology. It was found out that the participants had tried to be adaptable with the situation, they made use of what's available in their end, some also had chosen to reach out their peers for help and did some self-exploration. Aside to these, the pre-service teachers also tried to endure amid their limitation and dealt squarely any challenge they were in.

It was found out that the pre-service teachers tried to be adaptable with the situation. It supported the study of Laguitao *et.al* (2021) which stated that the pandemic has made the teachers and learners adapt to new technologies and maximize their experiences and abilities in the new normal set-up. The pre-service in their study has

also opted to adapt with the new normal by embracing them in their midst as they believe that this is the new normal of education. This is also seen as an avenue to maximize their potentials being 21st century educators.

Making use of what's available is another way for the participants to deal with their difficulties on the use of technology. In the absence of personal laptop and computer, the participants made use of mobile phones which were the only available gadgets they had instead. It bolstered the study of Kapasia, Paul, Roy, Saha, Zaveri, Mallick, Barman, Das and Chouhan (2020) which found that most of the students used android mobile for attending their classes online. Another study also implied that mobile phones are well-liked by students and became one of the best tools for an educational institution to adopt in the new normal.

In online teaching, the pre-service teachers also had reached out to their peers for help and motivation in times of their struggles. Colbeck, Sakulwichitsintu, Turner and Ellis (2014) study was supported by this as they confided that different students have different learning potential and intelligence, with this, some students need peers' motivation or support for further exchanging their own ideas and opinions. Moreover, they added that online students could also contribute to their peers through encouragement and facilitation while interacting with each other

Doing self-exploration is also practiced by the pre-service teachers in order to cope with their challenges in using technology. This supports Coman *et.al* (2020) who said that in online teaching, the teachers who are open minded, flexible and interested in developing themselves became self-taught and tried to improve their teaching skills online education. However, a certain segment of teachers still manifests resilience towards learning how to use new tools and they use, during the courses, only the basic functions of the E-learning platform

Moreover, the pre-service teachers also tried to endure amid their limitation in order to continue the student's learning. It braced to the claim that to counter the recent negative experiences of online education, Openo (2020) believed that the long-term champions of online education must confront the three biggest challenges that still face online instruction –interactivity, authenticity, and support. By confronting and enduring these challenges now, while teaching online is part of the new normal, faculty and their institutions can help online education mature to achieve its potential and promise.

Dealing squarely any challenges at hand is the last resort the pre-service teachers had utilized in their difficulties to the technology. In the study of Coman *et.a.* (2020), satisfaction towards exclusively online learning show that, in spite of all problems encountered, the learners had the ability to relate these problems to the context of the pandemic when both teachers and students were forced to deal with a situation they hadn't faced before. Thus, some teachers also did try to learn, to find solutions, to offer support for students and to adapt their teaching style to the new conditions, things that some students appreciated despite the existing technical problems. Hence, seeing the short period of time in which teachers had to adapt to the new teaching conditions, most of them managed to cope successfully with the challenges, but there is still room for improvement.

Assistance from School, Administration and Cooperating Teachers. The emerging themes in this structured theme are: guidance from the cooperating teacher, getting techniques from cooperating teacher, getting personal help from administration and cooperating teacher, flexibility of school and administration, administration provided classrooms, school as venue for learning, scholarship from school, get support from administration for online teaching and free internet connection from school.

Guidance from the cooperating teacher has been one of the assistance given to the pre-service teachers in their teaching practicum. In the study of Hadijah and Shalawati (2021), the findings reveal some issues being encountered by the pre-service teachers in planning and performing their online teaching activities. Meanwhile, the guidance and feedbacks from the teacher-educator help them to develop their skills in planning and managing online teaching.

In the same way, getting techniques from the cooperating teacher was also practiced by the pre-service teachers which they considered as help in their practicum. It backed the study of Hadijah and Shalawati (2021) where the pre-service teachers received trainings and techniques in lesson planning as well as delivering of the lessons. As stated, after they have completed their lesson plans, their teacher-educator checked their lesson plans' quality based on the components. Afterwards, some revisions are required after receiving some feedbacks from the teacher-educator.

Getting personal help from administration and cooperating teacher also took place during their teaching practicum. As stated by Fafunwa (2001), a faculty of education should help students grow, develop, and equip them with the necessary skills and professional abilities to become effective teachers. In the study of Salima and Hamzah (2020), if the students have not understood the lesson, the teacher would ask students to contact him personally and to meet the teacher personally at school and hold discussions.

Flexibility of school and administration has given much help also to the pre-service teachers. In the online learning, the learners were given their own time at their own comfort and flexibility. This flexibility as claimed by Basilaia and Kvavadze (2020) was found to be more effective as learners submit their outputs at the given time providing answers to every query raised by them.

Another help that were given by the administration to the pre-service teachers is the classroom and the school as venue for learning as well as giving of support for their online teaching. As explained by Mercado (2008) that online learning programs must include a systematic planning process, designing, and implementing a learning environment easily accessible to students. However, it is still recommended as supported by Baluyos (2021) that the administrators must continue to upgrade the facilities and software used in online learning in the university and to increase bandwidth allocation for online classes to ensure stable connectivity of the instructors while having their synchronous classes. Also, in order to help the struggling instructors, they recommend to send instructors to training and workshops on the new trends in assessing students' performance using online platform/software.

Another assistance that was given by the school to pre-service teachers is the scholarship. According to the University of Hawaii Foundation (2015), scholarships decrease the number and amount of loans students need to take to complete higher education. Supported by the study conducted by Daz, Dela Cruz, Ferrer, and Gonzales

(2016) at the University of the East – Caloocan, results found that the scholarship is beneficial. It was also found out that the scholarship lessen the daily expenses as a student. Based on the data, the researchers found that scholarship grants are important, for the reason that it helps the students who are experiencing financial problem. Also, students state that financial assistance is a need for the students to support their needs.

Free internet connection from school was also given to the pre-service teachers. This free internet connection is a project of the government “Free Wifi For All”. The pre-service teachers can access this free wifi if they are within the school premises. This supports the recommendation of Asio *et.al.* 2021 where the provision of pocket Wifi for students especially in far-flung areas with ample data connection must be given by the school. Also, provision of Wifi hotspots to certain locations where students can avail it for free in the community like a plaza, barangay halls, Barangay Police outposts, parks, etc. is being recommended.

Insights Gained with Experience in Teaching English Online. The emerging themes in this structured theme are: it pays to be a good intern, online teaching is really challenging, be an open-minded teacher, teaching is not an easy profession and good preparation works.

The experiences of the pre-service teachers during their teaching practicum gained insights and realizations. They realized that one has to pay in order to become a good intern and that teaching is not an easy profession. Moreover, they also realized that as a teacher one has to be open-minded. They also grasped that once you have prepared well in your lesson, it will always result well in the class.

It pays to be a good intern is the first insight that was gained by the pre-service teachers. As Ambrosetti (2014) stated as a support in this idea, practicum is a shared journey between the mentor teacher and the pre-service teacher. Proper pre-service teacher training, strong teaching practicum foundation, and a good guidance and monitoring from the mentor teachers should be well-considered in order to better prepare the student-teachers become qualified teachers in the future.

The pre-service teachers also had realized after their online English teaching practicum that online teaching is really challenging. In the study of Laguitao *et.al* (2021) they said that online learning is challenging as to some factors that need to be considered such as the connectivity, area, and of course, the monetary consideration or financial capability of both teachers and learners. They also claimed that going online in education at the early shifts of the pandemic is indeed exigent. As concluded, it is in this premise that the pre-service teachers, their participants, see the connection between their internet infrastructures and their productivity.

Being an open-minded teacher is also an insight of the pre-service teachers during their teaching internship. As Coman *et.al* (2020) stated that teachers who are open minded in developing themselves became self-taught and tried to improve their teaching skills. However also, a certain segment of teachers still manifests resilience towards learning how to use new tools and they use, during the courses, only the basic functions of the E-learning platform.

Teaching is not an easy profession as the pre-service teachers had also perceived. Such insight supports Naylor, Campbell-Evan and Maloney (2015) who said that learning to teach is a complex process because of the roles and responsibilities that

teachers have to play, the nature of schools and classrooms and the diversity of students.

Lastly, the pre-service teachers had proven that good preparation works in every teaching endeavor. It strengthened Ulla (2016) who mentioned that course teachers and supervising teachers should monitor, help, and teach them how to develop teaching materials to be used in class. The pre-service teachers revealed that knowledge on how to plan, prepare and develop teaching materials in the class is an important skill that should be learned. They further said that the lack of skills in planning and preparing a lesson, and developing teaching materials can lead to ineffective teaching.

Things Needed during the Implementation of Online Teaching. The emerging themes in this structured theme are: find ways to connect to students online, preparation of lessons, consider the learning of the child, establish gap between teachers and students.

The challenges of the pre-service teachers during their teaching practicum had brought out the ideas needed to be addressed in the implementation of online teaching. They believed that the teachers should find ways to connect to the students online in this trying times and to consider their learnings. They also find it necessary to prepare the lessons before going online for classes and to establish gap between their learners.

Teachers must find ways to connect to students online is another consideration that the learners find essential during the implementation of online teaching. It backed the study of Tham and Werner (2005) which results revealed that the effectiveness of E-learning is determined by three elements. One of these elements is the students. Since the students may feel isolated because of the absence of physical colleagues, the teachers should know how to establish and find ways to build connections and relationships with them.

Also, the preparation of lessons is needed to be considered during the implementation of online learning as perceived by the pre-service teachers. In the study of Baluyos (2021), she claimed that teaching in an online learning environment necessitates more preparation than teaching in a traditional classroom. It is because the quality of online learning education may be influenced by how teachers are prepared to teach. Thus ample preparation, enough time, and resources should be extended to instructors (Gurley, 2018). Instructors should learn, develop, and model the necessary knowledge, skills, and dispositions relevant to online learning environments (Williams, and Casale, 2015). Moreover, Baluyos (2021) has emphasized that instructors should be given enough time and resources in the preparation of learning materials. In addition, these learning materials should be carefully planned and aligned to the outcomes of the lesson. Students will acquire skills to analyze, synthesize, and develop their logical reasoning and creative thinking through learning materials.

Another consideration needed by the pre-service teachers in the implementation of the online teaching is the learning of the child. It bolstered Coman *et.al* (2021) as they revealed that when using E-learning platforms, there should be some elements that might be considered obstacles in students' process of learning, such as decreased motivation in students, delayed feedback or help due to the fact that their teachers are

not always available at the time students may need help while learning, or feelings of isolation due to lack of physical presence of classmates. Which is why, these obstacles can only be overcome with the help of teachers who should adapt their teaching strategies to the needs of students for it is the reason in the first place of why teaching takes place.

To establish a gap between teachers and students is the last consideration that the pre-service teachers think is needed during the implementation of online learning. To establish a gap means to put a boundary like respect on the relationship between teacher and students. The teachers must not assume that being kind and respectful to students is enough to bolster achievement. An ideal classroom has more than a single goal: therefore, teachers must hold students to appropriately high standards of academic performance and offer students opportunity for an emotional connection to their teachers, their fellow students and the school (Gregory and Weinstein, 2004; Wentzel, 2010). This is supported in the study of Tormey (2021) who emphasized that warmth should not be seen as unimportant—rather that warmth, trust, and admiration are seen together as elements of a re-imagined and less exploitative conceptualization of care work.

Assistance to be Provided from the School, the Administrator and the Cooperating Teachers to Pre-service Teachers for their Professional Life. The emerging themes in this structured theme are: training for teaching strategies, provision for internet connection, introduce more challenging tasks, cooperating teacher as role model, guidance from cooperating teacher and cooperating teachers gave all the support.

Upon completion of their teaching practicum, the pre-service teachers had come up with few necessary factors that they believed would assist them more in their teaching. They believed, that few of the assistance they needed from the school, the administration and the cooperating teachers are trainings the teaching strategies in teaching English for them to become more efficient in teaching. They also believed that they should be given provision in the internet connection as this is one of their common challenges as well as to task them a more challenging responsibilities. Moreover, they also see it as a need that the cooperating teachers should model to them the strategies and guide them more in teaching.

The pre-service teachers believed that they should be given training for teaching strategies for them to become more efficient in teaching. As Hadijah and Shalawati (2021) had revealed in their study, in giving assessment, it is one of the challenging parts in online teaching activities, especially in giving tasks and monitoring the students' activities in completing the task honestly. That is why, providing the pre-service teachers the training on how to assess online learning activities becomes necessary for the pre-service teachers because they still have limited knowledge on this aspect. It is also suggested for the pre-service and in-service teachers to know effective assessment application that can be effectively given to the students and ease the teachers' efforts in designing, monitoring and checking the tasks for the students.

Since the stability of the internet connection is the biggest predictor of success in online teaching, provision for internet connection must also be considered. This supported Fernandez (2020) who expressed that stable internet connections and

functional gadgets like laptops, computers, and mobile phone should be deliberated in the online teaching-learning process as important. More so, Baluyos (2021) believed that there is a need for an updated gadget and a stable platform/software for online classes. These may help them especially in synchronous classes. Instructors still need support from the institution as they continue to deliver quality online education to learners, as evident in their experience in difficulty in the conduct of assessment activities in online teaching.

Another thing that the pre-service teachers believe is needed for them to become ready in teaching is introducing to them more challenging tasks. It backed up Lortie (2002) who implied that with the given serious implications on pre-service teachers' naïve mental models, he calls upon teacher educators to come up with approaches that will help beginners increase their awareness. As teachers, they have the responsibility to use best practices in college teaching to offer learning experiences for that will give the pre-service teachers the opportunities to develop more grounded, more constructive understandings of what it means to teach and learn.

In addition, the pre-service teachers also consider it as big help when their cooperating teachers model to them the strategies and techniques in teaching. This corroborated Williams and Casale (2015) who noted that the instructors should learn, develop, and model the necessary knowledge, skills, and dispositions relevant to online learning environments in order for their learners to adapt them to themselves.

Another thing that the pre-service teachers considered as needed is the guidance from their cooperating teacher. Nagro, Hirsch and Kennedy (2020) stated that guidance is required to facilitate pre-service teachers' evaluation of their methods during cycles of reflective practice. For example, guiding questions orient their focus on the analysis of teaching choices and why they do what they do, evaluation of the success or failure of those choices based on students' learning outcomes, and implementation of revised plans for future lessons.

However, to all the assistances that were brought out, one pre-service believed that the cooperating teachers had already gave all the support needed by them. This is supported by iNACOL (2011) who claimed that online teachers are tasked with not only teaching subject matter but also supporting students' engagement, interactions, and technological skills within the online environment which is already beyond their tasks. Which is why, in the study of Zweig and Stafford (2016), they emphasizes that since the teachers are tasked with both content instruction and supporting students within the online learning environment—an environment to which many are new—then there is a pressing need for more focus on supporting these teachers for professional development trainings. Thus, pre-service education programs and online learning programs should consider providing more opportunities for both current and future online teachers to build their knowledge and skills related to student perseverance and engagement.

Ways that the Experiences in Teaching English Online Prepare the Pre-service Teachers for their Teaching Profession. The emerging themes in this structured theme are: get some ideas on teaching, learned about the life of a teacher, learned some strategies and approaches and able to build confidence to face students.

The purpose of teaching internship is to prepare the pre-service teachers in the field. With the training provided to the pre-service teachers in this online practicum, the pre-service teachers believed that they were made ready because of four facts. Through their experiences, they get some ideas on how to teach by learning some strategies and approaches in language teaching. In addition, they have learned about the life as a teacher and have built confidence in facing their students.

The pre-service teachers, based on what were given to them as experience in teaching English online considered themselves prepared in teaching through some ideas on teaching that they get from their instructors and cooperating teachers. By simply observing during their classes, the pre-service teachers were able to learn from them. It substantiated Ugalingan, Edjan and Valdez (2021) who stated that the supervisor's role has been helpful as they modeled strategies and provided input in facilitating online teaching. The participants were able to observe their supervisors with the different online teaching strategies which they found effective as they also applied these during their tutorial sessions. In addition, as Aisyah and Wicaksono (2018) mentioned, one of the indicators of being a professional language teacher was developing the profession continually through reflective actions. It means that the pre-service teachers are already familiar with the process of online learning. Therefore, the pre-service teachers were considered aware of their preparation in implementing teaching online and developed answers to online learning difficulties.

Having to learn about the life of a teacher is another way which the pre-service teachers considers have prepared them in teaching. In the study of Sepulveda-Escobar et al. (2020), the pre-service teachers termed online teaching practicum as a "once-in-a-lifetime" experience which from their view impacts them positively for their teacher education and future careers. Through this practice which opened their eyes about the different role of the teachers, pre-service teachers will be more prepared for the real world where changes and adaptations are crucial to keep going and keep developing. Besides that, the experience of teaching practicum during the pandemic gave pre-service teachers an opportunity to put into test their teaching skills in addition to further exploring the skills to strengthen them (Sepulveda-Escobar and Morrison, 2020).

It was also revealed that by learning some strategies and approaches in teaching, the pre-service teachers are now prepared in teaching. In fact, the pre-service teachers are also equipped with teaching online experiences, making them imitate their lecturers' teaching strategies and methods for their perceived readiness in teaching practice programs in an online environment. Moreover, the PSTs were also able to receive mentoring and feedback after each tutorial for further improvement. As a means of socio-emotional support, these practices have helped create a level of familiarity for the participants in eventually handling actual classes (Hadar, Ergas, Alpert and Ariav, 2020).

Lastly, due to their experience in teaching, the pre-service teachers had built confidence to face students. They believe that they were being prepared to teach as they were given the experience to handle and manage their students. This corroborated the study of O'Neill and Stephenson (2012) who claim that classroom management subjects increase pre-service teachers' confidence and preparedness to manage their own classroom.

Conclusions

With the English online teaching as the main focus of the investigation, the understanding on the experiences, the challenges encountered, mechanisms utilized in coping with the challenges, and insights of the English pre-service teachers, and crafted intervention program from the findings of the study in teaching English online was highlighted. The experience of the English pre-service teachers in teaching English online, drawn from their experiences, could reinforce the teachers, the administration and the institution's understanding about it.

The results showed that the pre-service teachers have difficulties in teaching English online due to problems caused by their unpreparedness to the pandemic, the difficulty with internet connection, availability of devices to be used, the preparation of themselves as well as to their learning materials. With this, the pre-service teachers had tried to be adaptable with the circumstances. Some did self-exploration and some reached out to their peers for help. There were also assistance from the institution and cooperating teachers that were given in forms of guidance and provision on the use of the classrooms and internet. Through their experiences, the pre-service teachers had known the reality of being a teacher and how to become a good one.

Reasonably, during the implementation of online learning, there are many things that need consideration. It is critical for the institution and administration as well as teachers to know the difficulties and struggles it may bring to the pre-service teachers. Administration and teachers should make sure that the pre-service teachers will be given support by means of trainings and workshops in teaching online, knowing that online teaching is new to them. Moreover, provision on internet connection and devices should also be deliberated as some of the participants honestly conveyed their difficulties on the materials needed in teaching online. To that effect, it would be of great help for the pre-service teachers to receive any form of support and guidance from the school, the administration and their cooperating teachers in preparing them into becoming a real teacher in the future.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following implications for practice are offered.

On the Description of Experiences as Pre-service Teacher Teaching English Online. It can be reckoned that the research participants had different description on their experiences in teaching English online as pre-service teachers. The definition of their experiences mentioned were considerably difficult, struggling, fulfilling, stressful, a different experience compared to face to face, delighted to teach, tense feeling but exciting, and challenging. Meanwhile, these descriptions were based on the experiences they had during their teaching internship.

According to the findings, the pre-service teachers mostly defined their experiences as difficult, stressful and challenging which are undeniably negative. This was because they had done so much adjustment during their internship due to factors related to online teaching. It has been shown that the pre-service teachers were

somewhat unprepared as they had not seen the online teaching practicum coming. However, the need to correct this impression is needed as teaching practicum always comes whether a pre-service teacher is prepared or not. Also, by further giving them more online preparatory teaching activities may also be advantageous for them so that there will be a minor room for them for adjustment.

On Preparations Made in Teaching English Online. The results implied that the pre-service teachers have made preparations in teaching English online by means of self-preparation, preparation of learning materials and ensure better internet connection. Hence, to teach English online requires preparations. Thus, the results showed that the pre-service teachers had made themselves prepared first, their learning materials as well as their devices and internet connection knowing that they will be teaching online.

The results also implied that a pre-service teacher must make good preparations for one to deliver his lessons well. Thus, good preparation correlates to self-confidence in teaching. Moreover, teachers must prepare his devices and always prepare for an option. Because no matter how much prepared you are in terms of self and learning materials, if you fail to prepare your online devices, you may fail in your online teaching too. Lastly, the teacher must also consider their students' capacity to connect themselves online knowing that there were students who also have challenges with regards the internet connectivity.

On College Programs that Help Pre-service Student in Teaching English Online. The findings of the study revealed the programs in college that helped the English pre-service teachers in their preparation for online teaching. Based on the result, the pre-service teachers get some learning from their demo teaching, get some learning from their subject, get some learning from their instructors, and nothing at all.

The implication of this is that the college institution had not provided any specific program that specifically prepared the pre-service teachers for online teaching. However, due to some subjects in their curriculum and their instructors who initiated demo practices, the pre-service teachers were introduced to online teaching which they consider as helpful during their teaching practicum. Hence, the institution should be developing detailed training and specific program that would help the pre-service teachers in their preparation for the online teaching practicum.

On Difficulties Encountered in the Teaching and Learning Process. The problem with the internet connectivity, difficulty with the delivery of subject online, problem with students' learning, problem with the preparation, lesson preparations and familiarity with English language are just few of the many difficulties being encountered by the pre-service teachers in teaching English online.

The problem with the internet connectivity is generic to all. However, the difficulties in the delivery of the lesson as well as the preparation for it has something to do with the knowledge and skills of the pre-service teachers. This appears that a pre-service teacher still has to learn more on the approaches and techniques in language teaching. Aside to this, a pre-service teacher should emerge himself more in learning more vocabularies and words as this is necessary as a language teacher. Moreover, a pre-service teacher should also begin to practice on speaking the English language since English should be his medium of instruction when teaching.

On Difficult English Lessons to Teach Online. Among the English lessons, the pre-service teachers considered the subject-verb agreement, vocabulary, lessons in literature and proper pronunciation as the lessons that are difficult to teach. Few participants too have found no difficult English lesson during their online practicum. This implies that even if the pre-service teacher already had studied English for three years in college, his learnings still continued even until he was practice teaching.

Teaching English lessons online is indeed challenging especially when one lacks knowledge about his topic. Which is why, as a teacher, one must master his lesson before teaching them to the students. As a proverb says, "You cannot give what you do not have." It is like telling, "You cannot teach what you do not know". Aside to this, one has to get himself involve too in reading books or articles to develop vocabulary learning. Also, learn to practice in speaking the English language as this is also important as a language teacher.

On Challenges Encountered with Technology in the Delivery of English Lessons. The pre-service teachers had experienced difficulties with technology in the delivery of their English lessons. These difficulties were literacy on the use of technology, poor internet connection, challenges in looking for online resources, cheating in the internet and malfunctioning laptop.

As the teaching was done online, the pre-service teachers who were not so knowledgeable with technology really had struggled on using technology in delivering their lessons. They had looked for any possible means in order for them to do their tasks and that involved reaching their peers out or searching in the YouTube. This implies that the pre-service teachers should be given prior understanding or training on the use of the online class applications like Google classroom and Google drive. Also, the pre-service teachers had struggled in looking for online resources due to the slow internet connection, which in order to give help, the institution should have provided them any means to have resources needed in teaching English, or should have provided them with already downloaded PDFs or articles or e-books for them to be guided.

On Causes of the Challenges Encountered. The results of this study have shown that the pre-service teachers considered that poor internet connection, being unfamiliar with word meaning, curriculum is still new, lack of budget for internet connection, improper delivery of lessons, unprepared for the pandemic and being new to online modality are the causes of their struggles in teaching English online.

Unpreparedness to the pandemic was shown as the root of most of the difficulties that the pre-service teachers had encountered in teaching English online. This also implies that the institution was not totally prepared on the new normal setting in education. Therefore, in order to help the pre-service teachers on these challenges, the institution should formulate programs and activities that would help the pre-service teachers be prepared for online teaching. They should be given training on the use of approaches and techniques to ensure that their online teaching experience will be successful. Thus, the administration should be mindful of the capacities of their pre-service teachers when it comes to gadgets and devices to be used.

On Mechanisms Utilized to Cope with Challenges Encountered. As pointed out by the participants, the ways in dealing with their challenges in teaching English online were study lessons first, determination in delivering the lesson, need for gadgets and

internet connection, develop learning materials, search for word meaning, engage students at the start of the session and use of interactive platform.

This implies that the pre-service teachers were determined and strong-minded with their tasks. The preparations they did in order to give learning to their students were obvious even in their difficulties when it comes to devices and internet connection.

When it comes to the teaching session, in order to overcome the barriers in teaching, it is therefore necessary for the English pre-service teachers to have trainings on the use of interactive platforms and so to engage their learners in their classes. Also, it would be best if the pre-service teachers will be given another training on how to develop meaningful and effective learning materials that can be utilized in an online classroom.

On Ways Used to Teach Difficult English Lessons. The results have an implication that students find ways to simplify lessons and do research in the internet. With regards to this, pre-service teachers should think for any language teaching strategy applicable for online teaching to be utilized in their classes. Also, it would be very useful for the pre-service teachers if they will be trained by the institution or the cooperating teachers with the different strategies in teaching English.

On Ways Used in Dealing with Difficulties on the Use of Technology. Because the difficulties in the use of technology, especially on the internet connectivity, the pre-service teachers had dealt with it by trying to be adaptable, making use of what's available, reaching out to peers, doing self-exploration, trying to endure amid the limitation and dealing squarely any challenge at hand.

The pre-service teachers dealt with their difficulties by means of being adaptable to the challenges. They made use of their mobile phones in teaching due to the absence of laptop which is more helpful if there is. Some had tried to reach out their peers for help and assistance and some did self-exploration. Moreover, the pre-service teachers had dealt their challenge at hand with positivity and determination knowing that these things were part of their trainings into their becoming.

With regards on this, the findings on this study therefore necessitates the administration to give help to the pre-service teachers through giving them assistance especially those who are in need for internet connectivity. Also, trainings on use for technology and online class application should also be provided to the pre-service teachers.

On Assistance from School, Administration and Cooperating Teachers. Due to the new setting in the education system, the pre-service teachers perceived that the school and the administration had given them assistance in terms of guidance from the cooperating teacher, getting techniques from cooperating teacher, getting personal help from administration and cooperating teacher, flexibility of school and administration, administration provided classrooms, school as venue for learning, scholarship from school, get support from administration for online teaching and free internet connection from school.

This assistance had somewhat brought comfort and satisfaction to the pre-service teachers. The guidance they had received from their cooperating teachers as well as the personal help they got from the administration were appreciated. Also, in extending the school classrooms as their venue for learning and demo teaching gave

them joy as they were able to feel that they were real teachers during these activities. The free wifi from the government was also a big help to them who struggled with internet connectivity. Also, through the scholarship they had with the institution, the pre-service teachers believe that it was a great help as through their allowances, they were able to avail devices like laptop and mobile phones that are essential in their online teaching.

However, even in these assistances given to pre-service teachers, the challenges in online learning and teaching process are still present and it has to be given address. With this, the administration is in need to give pre-service teachers regular face-to-face sessions or trainings that would help them prepare in the online teaching. The cooperating teachers must do personal observation to the pre-service teachers and give feedback right away. These are necessary so for them to see and address the real struggles of the pre-service teachers during this trying season.

On Insights Gained with Experience in Teaching English Online. The pre-service teachers had gained few insights from their experiences in teaching English online. They realized that it pays to be a good intern, online teaching is really challenging, that a teacher should be an open-minded teacher, that teaching is not an easy profession and that good preparation works.

These insights were gained based on their challenges in their teaching practicum. The findings showed that their experiences in their online teaching opened their eyes on the reality of the life of a teacher. That being a teacher is not an easy profession and teaching is really challenging. In addition, the pre-service teachers also believe that good preparation will result to good teaching experience. With these, they realized that in order to become a good one, pre-service teachers has to pay much effort and determination in their works.

With these, the institution and the cooperating teachers should made intensive trainings and workshop in order to carefully help and assist the pre-service teachers in their roles as teachers. There should be seminars to be given to them in preparing effective learning materials that they could use in their online classes.

On Things Needed during the Implementation of Online Teaching. As perceived by the pre-service teachers, the things needed to be considered on the implementation of online teaching are teachers should find ways to connect to students online, preparation of lessons, consider the learning of the child and to establish gap between teachers and students.

Based on their experiences, the pre-service teachers believed that as online teachers, they should find ways in connecting to their students online knowing that the same difficulty with the internet connection is also experienced by the learners. This implies that there should be consideration to be given to learners who have issues with connectivity. Also, lesson preparations should be given ample time since in online teaching, various materials are needed which implies many preparations too. Additionally, as online teachers, one should think of the learning that the child may get in the online class. There has to be activities that would usher the different preferred learnings of the students. This implies that the teachers should design differentiated activities for the different types of learners. Lastly, the pre-service teachers should be trained on how manage an online class as some of the learners may think negatively on them as practice teachers only.

On Assistance to be Provided from the School, the Administrator and the Cooperating Teachers to Pre-service Teachers for their Professional Life. As perceived by the pre-service teachers, the assistance needed to be provided by the school, the administrator and cooperating teachers for their professional lives are training for teaching strategies, provision for internet connection, introduce more challenging tasks, cooperating teacher as role model, guidance from cooperating teacher and cooperating teachers gave all the support.

The need for training for teaching strategies was the cry of the pre-service teachers as they believe that the strategies they acquire in their academic subjects were strategies in teaching a face-to-face classes. There might be some strategies that are applicable, yet the struggle was still inexplicable. This implies that the institution should be designing trainings on online teaching strategies to better help the pre-service teachers in this difficulty. Also, pre-service teachers believe that as pre-service teachers, they must be given provision with internet connection as this is a factor necessary in teaching online. This implies that they must be given other means aside from the “free wifi” in the school since they are also teaching. Means might be in a form of load allowance or router.

The pre-service teachers also consider that they should be given a more challenging task so to prepare them in their profession. Because some of the pre-service teachers were given lessons that is not an English lesson, they were deprived with the experience to teach lesson of their own specialization. This implies that the tasks that must be given to them must be based on the curriculum of the high school, and not just subjects that are not related to their course. Moreover, in order to become prepared in the field of teaching, the pre-service teachers should have been provided constant and hands-on guidance from their cooperating teachers. This means that a face to face interaction with the cooperating teachers in this online worlds should be considered. By this, the pre-service teachers can get feedbacks and learnings through their cooperating teachers.

On Ways that the Experiences in Teaching English Online Prepare the Pre-service Teachers for their Teaching Profession. Based on the result of the experiences of the pre-service teachers in teaching English online, they believed that though some ideas they get on teaching, their learnings about the life of a teacher and learning on some strategies and approaches, these experiences prepared them for their teaching profession. They also believed that through these experiences, they were able to build confidence to face their students which helped them also to become prepared in their teaching profession.

The pre-service teachers consider that through the ideas they get on their experiences, they were made prepared in teaching. This implies that by actively teaching online, they received ideas on how to teach and address the needs of their learners. Also, through their online practicum, they were given realization about the teacher’s life which they also believe, is an eye-opener for them on the reality of being a teacher. By teaching English online, the pre-service teachers also learned some strategies and techniques in handling and managing the learners online, which they believe is another factor that prepared them in their chosen profession. Moreover, their online teaching practicum also enables them to build confidence to themselves in teaching learners online. These imply that the teaching practicum experiences of the

pre-service teachers significantly gave them ideas and techniques on how to become a good and effective teacher online.

Implications for Future Research

Inasmuch as the study was limited to the responses of the English pre-service teachers in Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology, Trento External Studies Center, Purok 4 Poblacion, Trento, Agusan del Sur, the following implications for future research are considered:

First, future research may be conducted by selecting other groups of pre-service teachers, not only focusing on the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English students but the other education courses as well. Second, another research of the same focus may be conducted to another location to explore the same phenomenon on teaching English online. Third, change of research participants to in-service teachers may be conducted to explore the insight or understanding of the in-service teachers about teaching English online to find out whether the insights of English pre-service teachers matches to insights of the in-service teachers. Fourth, this study was done in a public college. Further research could be done to explore the same phenomenon among private colleges. Fifth, the research participant mentioned using again the formal and informal theme. There should be research to be conducted as to the effectiveness of self-preparation, preparation of learning materials, ensuring better internet connection, studying the lessons first, determination in delivering the lesson, developing learning materials, searching for word meaning, engaging the students at the start of the session and using of interactive platform in teaching English online. Sixth, informants proposed trainings for teaching strategies, provision for internet connection, introduce more challenging tasks, cooperating teacher as role model and guidance from cooperating teachers. With regards to this, there should be a conduct of research about having the efficacy of these programs for the students. Seventh, there should be research on the making and developing quality assurance of online teaching materials. Finally, the research could be conducted to explore the curriculum, as well as the school program, by highlighting the evaluation to the English pre-service teachers during their teaching English online.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The goal of being informed and giving full voluntary consent must be achieved. A letter addressed to the College President and Campus Administrator was secured before the conduct of the In-depth Interview with the participants. Before the pre-service teachers were considered as participants, consent was given and explained to them. They were clarified that their participation was voluntary and does not affect their job. The researcher ensured that they knew very well the benefit and risk they would get for their involvement. And that anytime when they wish to withdraw or would like to stop from the interview, they may do so. Thus, they were assured that the information was solely used for the study only.

The researcher also informed the participants before signing the consent that the study wanted to find out their experiences, challenges and coping mechanisms to further know their insights on their English online teaching, which participants was considered for In- Depth Interview to give clearer explanation on their experiences. The interview was done after the participants have signed the consent and have done in the specified time and venue which the participants are comfortable with. Lastly, pseudonyms were used in order to keep their identities private.

Acknowledgments

The researcher has taken hard work for the success of this study. However, this study would not have been made possible without the fervent prayer, undying support and selfless help of many individuals who have imparted big contribution to finish this undertaking.

To the Dean of Graduate Studies of Assumption College of Nabunturan, Roel P. Villocino, EdD., the chairman of the examining committee and to the panel of the examiners, Felinita R. Doronio, MAEd, MEdStud and Elizabeth D. Dioso, Ed.D., for giving their kind comments and meticulous analysis for the improvement and betterment of this research study;

To Dhan Timothy M. Ibojo, PhD., her adviser and mentor, for his constant support and provision in her thesis journey. For sharing his time and expertise in checking even to the smallest detail of this manuscript. Without him, this study would not have been realized;

To her Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology, Trento Satellite Campus (ASSCAT, TSC) family, her colleagues and friends, Jacky Lyn, Ryan Christian, Marilyn, Donna Faye, Veligen and Mylene, for their words of encouragement that touch her heart to really go extra miles in this endeavor;

To Jesus For All- House of Prayer church, her spiritual family and comfort. For their prayers and declaration of strength, wisdom and provision to the researcher which she appreciates the most. Their constant "Amen" to her desire of finishing this course;

To her beloved parent, Papa Tersing in heaven and Mama Conching. To her siblings, Joan, Adriano, Angela, Princess Joy and Novien Yccine, for their unconditional love and never-ending support in her life's journey. From where she came to where she will become, they remained her strong portion.

To her husband, Jeffrey, for his boundless love expressed through his kind words of motivation and the laying of his hands in prayer to her. To all the small yet significant acts he showed to her as his support and help, she is forever grateful to him and his love.

Above all, to her Almighty God in Three Person, the Father, the Son Jesus, and the Holy Spirit, for His sustaining grace and abounding love. The fountain of life, joy, hope, strength, wisdom and good health. Without Him, she cannot do anything on her own. Glory to Him alone!

REFERENCES

- Agung A and Surtikanti, M. (2020). "Students' Perception of Online Learning during COVID-19 Pandemic: A Case Study on the English Students of STKIP Pamane Talino," *SOSHUM J. Sos. dan Hum.*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 225–235, 2020, doi: 10.31940/soshum.v10i2.1316.
- Aisyah, A., & Wicaksono, B. H. (2018). Pre-service teachers' belief on professional development: A study on ESP teacher. *Celtic: A Journal of Culture, English Language Teaching, Literature and Linguistics*, 5(2), 8-17.
<https://ejournal.umm.ac.id/index.php/celtic/article/view/7614>
- Ambrosetti, A. (2014). Are You Ready to be a Mentor? Preparing Teachers for Mentoring Pre-service Teachers. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 39(6).<http://dx.doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2014v39n6.2>
- Ardiyansah, T. Y. (2021). PreService Teachers' Perceived Readiness in Teaching Online in International Internship Program. *Celtic: A Journal of Culture, English Language Teaching, Literature and Linguistics*, 8(1), 90-102.
- Atmojo, A and Nugroho, A. (2020) "EFL Classes Must Go Online! Teaching Activities and Challenges during COVID-19 Pandemic in Indonesia," *Regist. J.*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 49–76, 2020, doi: 10.18326/rgt.v13i1.49-76
- Backfisch, I., Lachner, A., Stürmer, K., and Scheiter, K. (2021a). Variability of teachers' technology integration in the classroom: a matter of utility! *Comput. Educ.* 166:104159. doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2021.104159
- Baluyos, G. (2020). Experiences of Instructors in Online Teaching: A phenomenological Study. September 2021. DOI:10.35877/454RI.eduline542
- Barnesa, R., Hall, R., Lower, V., Pottinger, C. & Popham, A. (2020). Lessons from an An online teacher preparation Program: flexing work experience to meet student needs and regulators' requirements in the United States. *Journal of Education for Teaching*.
- Basilaia, G. & Kvavadze, D. (2020). Transition to online education in schools during a SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in Georgia. *Pedagogical Research*, 5(4).
- Black, K. (2010) "Business Statistics: Contemporary Decision Making" 6th edition, John Wiley & Sons.
- Boyce, C. and Neale, P. (2006) *Conducting In-Depth Interview: A Guide for Designing and Conducting In-Depth Interviews for Evaluation Input*. Pathfinder International Tool Series, Monitoring and Evaluation-2.
http://www.pathfind.org/site/DocServer/m_e_tool_series_indepth_interviews.pdf?docID=6301
- Cleofas, J.V., & Rocha, I.C.N. (2021). Demographic, gadget, and internet profiles as determinants of disease and consequence related COVID-19 anxiety among Filipino college students. *Education and Information Technologies*,
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10529-9>
- Coman, C., Tîru, L., Schmitz, L., Stanciu, C. & Bularca, M. (2020). Online Teaching and Learning in Higher Education during the Coronavirus Pandemic: Students' Perspective. *Sustainability*. 2020.

- Creswell, J. W. (2007). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (2nd ed.). Sage Publications, Inc.
- Creswell, J. W. (2008). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (3rd ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Education, Inc.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative Inquiry & Research Design: Choosing among Five Approaches* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE.
- Creswell, J. (2015). *Educational Research: Planning, Conducting, and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research*. New York: Pearson.
- Colbeck, Douglas & Sakulwichitsintu, Songlak & Turner, Paul & Ellis, Leonie. (2014). *Online Peer Learning: Understanding Factors Influencing Students' Learning Experience*.
- Daz, A., Dela Cruz, K., Ferrer, J., & Gonzales, E. 2016. "The impact of Scholarship Program to the Grade 11 students of University of The East – Caloocan". University of the East- Caloocan Campus
- Demuyakor, J. (2020). Coronavirus (covid -19) and online learning in higher institutions of education: a survey of the perceptions of Ghanaian international-students-in-china. *Online Journal of Communication and Media Technologies*, 10(3).
- Deocampo, M. (2020). Issues and Challenges of English Language Teacher-Trainees' Teaching Practicum Performance: Looking Back and Going Forward. *LEARN Journal: Language Education and Acquisition Research Network Journal*, Volume 13, Issue 2, July 2020
- Dhawan, S. (2020). Online Learning: A panacea in the time of COVID-19 crisis. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems* 0(0), 1-18.
- Efriana, L. (2021). Problems of online learning during COVID-19 pandemic in EFL classroom and the solution. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Literature*, 2(1), 38-47. <https://jurnal.stkipmb.ac.id/index.php/jelita/article/view/74>
- Eksi, G. & Yeşilçınar, S. (2015) An Investigation of the Effectiveness of Online Text-to-Speech Tools in Improving EFL Teacher Trainees' Pronunciation. *English Language Teaching*. January 2016 9(2):205 DOI:10.5539/elt.v9n2p205
- Ersin, P., & Atay, D. (2021). Exploring online mentoring with preservice teachers in a pandemic and the need to deliver quality education. *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*.
- Esani, M. (2010). *Moving from Face-to-Face to Online Teaching*. Clinical Laboratory Sciences Program, University of Texas Medical Branch, Galveston, TX
- Estira, K.L.A. (2020). Online distance learning readiness of business administration students in one state university in the Philippines. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(12), 826-832.
- Fabito, B.S., Trillanes, A.O., & Sarmiento, J.R. (2021). Barriers and challenges of computing students in an online learning environment: Insights from one private university in the Philippines. *International Journal of Computing Sciences Research*, 5(1), 441-458. <https://doi.org/10.2514/ijcsr.2017.001.1.51>
- Febrianto, P., Mas'udah, S and Megasari, L. (2020) "Implementation of online learning during the covid-19 pandemic on Madura Island, Indonesia," *Int. J. Learn. Teach. Educ. Res.*, vol. 19, no. 8, pp. 233–254, 2020, doi: 10.26803/ijlter.19.8.13.

- Flores, I. (2015). Developing preservice teachers' self-efficacy through field-based science teaching practice with elementary students. *Research in Higher Education Journal*, 27 (2015), pp. 1-19
- Gregory, A., & Weinstein, R. S. (2008). The discipline gap and African Americans: Defiance and cooperation in the high school classroom. *The Journal of School Psychology*, 46(4), 455-475.
- Gurley, L. E. (2018). Educators' Preparation to Teach, Perceived Teaching Presence, and Perceived Teaching Presence Behaviors in Blended and Online Learning Environments. *Online learning*, 22(2), 197-220. Retrieved on November 10, 20202 from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1181399>
- Hadar, L.L., Ergas, O., Alpert, B., & Ariav, T. (2020). Rethinking teacher education in a VUCA world: Student teachers' social-emotional competencies during the Covid-19 crisis. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(4), 573-586. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2020.1807513>
- Hadijah, Sitti & Shalawati, Shalawati. (2021). Coaching Pre-Service Teachers in Planning and Teaching English Online. 10.2991/assehr.k.210914.002.
- Halim, T., Wahid, R. & Halim, S. (2021). Challenges of teaching and learning grammar in online classes at the tertiary level. *ELT Forum Journal of English Language Teaching*. November 2021. 10(3):212-221 DOI:10.15294/elt.v10i3.47970
- Hodges, Moore, Lockee, Trust and Bond. (2021). The Difference Between Emergency Remote Teaching and Online Learning. *Educause Review*.
- Howland, J.L. & Moore, J.L. (2002). Student perceptions as distance learners in Internet-based courses. *Distance Education*, 23(2), 183-196. Abstract retrieved November 18, 2003 from EBSCOHost Database.
- Islam, Z. (2021). Shift of English Literature Learning from Classroom to Online: Preferences and Attitude of Bangladeshi Undergraduate Students. *Elsya : Journal of English Language Studies* Vol. 3, No. 1, February 2021 , pp. 1-7 Available online at: <http://ojs.journal.unilak.ac.id/index.php/elsya>
- Jenkins, J. (2014). *Global Englishes: A resource book for students*. New York: Routledge
- Kaczor, B. (2007, September 26). Nearly 2 dozen Florida State athletes accused of cheating. *USA Today*. Retrieved from www.usatoday.com
- Kaldi, S. (2009). Student teachers' perceptions of self-competence in and emotions/stress about teaching in initial teacher education. *Educational Studies*, 35(3), 349–360.
- Kapasias, N., Paul, P., Roy, A., Saha, J., Zaveri, A., Mallick, R., Barman, B., Das, P., & Chouhan, P. (2020). Impact of lockdown on learning status of undergraduate and postgraduate students during COVID-19 pandemic in West Bengal, India. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 116, 105195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2020.105194>
- Koşar, Gulten. (2021) Distance Teaching Practicum: Its Impact on Pre-Service EFL Teachers' Preparedness for Teaching. Hatay Mustafa Kemal University. Turkey
- Laguitao, Cubalit, Teppang, dela Cruz & Bautista (2021). Plea from Within: The Plights of Pre-service Teachers in the Midst of the New Normal of Education. *American Journal of Educational Research*.

- Lakshaga Jyothi, M. (2021). Enabling Intelligence through Deep Learning using IoT in a Classroom Environment based on a multimodal approach. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(2), 381-393.
- Lawson, T., Çakmak, M., Gündüz, M & Busher, H. (2015) Research on teaching practicum – a systematic review. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 38 (3) (2015), pp. 392-407
- Lortie, D. (1975; 2002). *Schoolteacher* (2nd ed.) Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
- Martin, B. (2015). Successful implementation of tpack in teacher preparation programs. *Int. J. Integr. Tech. Educ.* 4, 17–26. doi: 10.5121/ijite.2015.4102
- Mercado, C. A. (2008). Readiness assessment tool for an e-learning environment implementation. Fifth International Conference on eLearning for KnowledgeBased Society. https://www.academia.edu/3294490/Readiness_Assessment_Tool_for_An_eLearning_Environment_Implementation.
- Mishraa, Gupta & Shree (2021). Online teaching-learning in higher education during lockdown period of COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Educational Research*
- Moten, J., Fitterer, A., Brazier, E., Leonard, J., & Brown, A. (2013). Examining online college cyber cheating methods and prevention measures. *Electronic Journal of eLearning*, 11(2), 139–146.
- Naah, A. M. . (2020). Pre-Service Teachers' Perception of Online Teaching and Learning During the COVID – 19 Era. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 8(10), 1649–1662. <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijstrm/v8i10.el01>
- Nagro, S. (2019). “Lesson Planning With Engagement in Mind: Proactive Classroom Management Strategies for Curriculum Instruction”. *Intervention in School and Clinic*. 54 (3): 131-140.
- Nagro, S. A., Hirsch, S. E., & Kennedy, M. J. (2020). A self-led approach to improving classroom management practices using video analysis. *Teaching Exceptional Children*, 53(1), 24–32.
- Naujoks, N., Bedenlier, S., Gläser-Zikuda, M., Kammerl, R., Kopp, B., Ziegler, A., et al. (2021). Self-regulated resource management in emergency remote higher education: status quo and predictors. *Front. Psychol.*
- Nation, I. S. P. (2001). *Learning vocabulary in another language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139524759>
- Naylor, D. A., Campbell-Evans, G., & Maloney, C. (2015). Learning to Teach: What Do Pre-service Teachers Report. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 40(11). <http://dx.doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2015v40n11.7>
- O'Neill, S. C. & Stephenson, J. (2012). Does classroom management coursework influence pre-service teachers' perceived preparedness or confidence? *Teaching and teacher education*, 28(8), 1131-114.
- Pastores, R., Dacanay, J., Mayoya, M., Nanglihan, M and Bautista, R. (2021). “All by Myself with Mr. Google: The Pandemic Education from the Lenses of Secondary School Students.” *American Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 9, no. 11 (2021): 660-664.

- Popova, L., and Pikulenko, M. (2020) "Teacher ' s Readiness to Create Own Online Courses," vol. 2020, pp. 2017–2031, 2020, doi: 10.3897/ap.2.e2017.
- Richter, D., Kunter, M., Lüdtke, O., Klusmann, U., Anders, Y & Baumert, J. (2013). How different mentoring approaches affect beginning teachers' development in the first years of practice. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 36 (2013), pp. 166-177
- Sailer, M., Murböck, J., and Fischer, F. (2021). Digital learning in schools: what does it take beyond digital technology? *Teach. Teach. Educ.* 103:1. doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2021.103346
- Salima, A & Hamzah. (2020). Teachers' Solution in English Online Learning Process for Senior High School Students in Pandemic Era. Atlant Press. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, volume 579
- Secret Teacher (2020). Teacher network: Resources, jobs and professional development for teachers. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/teacher>
- Sun, L.; Tang, Y.; Zuo, W. Coronavirus pushes education online. *Nat. Mater.* 2020, 19, 687.
- Tormey, R. Rethinking student-teacher relationships in higher education: a multidimensional approach. *High Educ* 82, 993–1011 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-021-00711-w>
- Ugalingan G., Edjan D & Valdez, P. (2021) Online Internship Experiences Among Pre-service ESL Teachers in the Philippines: Challenges and Opportunities. November 2021 — Volume 25, Number 3
- Ulla, M. (2016). Pre-service Teacher Training Programs in the Philippines: The Student-teachers Practicum Teaching Experience. November 2016 *EFL Journal* 1(3) DOI:10.21462/eflj.v1i3.23
- Valtonen, T., Kukkonene, J., Kontkanen, S., Sormunen, K., Dillon, P., and Sointu, E. (2015). The impact of authentic learning experiences with ICT on pre-service teachers' intentions to use ICT for teaching and learning. *Comput. Educ.* 81, 49–58. doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2014.09.008
- Vonderwell, S. (2003). An examination of asynchronous communication experiences and perspectives of students in an online course: A case study. *Internet and Higher Education*, 6(1), 77-90.
- Wentzel, K. (2010). Students' relationships with teachers. In J. L. Meece, & J. S. Eccles (Eds.), *Handbook of research on schools, schooling, and human development* (pp. 75-91). New York: Routledge.
- Williams, N. V., & Casale, M. J. (2015). The Preparation of Teacher Candidates for K-12 Online Learning Environments: A Case Study. *Mid-Western Educational Researcher*, 27(2). Retrieved on November 10, 20202 from <https://tinyurl.com/jepbavhs25>
- Yra, J.F.P., Castillo, R.H., Bautista, R.G., Camayang, J.G., & Camayang, A.G.G. (2020). Students' online learning readiness and internet connectivity: Bases for the customization of QSU e-Aral. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 8(11), 878-894. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-8-11-8>
- Zayapragassarazan, Z. (2020), "COVID-19: Strategies for Online Engagement of Remote Learners," F1000Research, no. April, 2020, doi: 10.7490/F1000RESEARCH.1117835.1.

- Zawacki-Richter, O. (2020). The current state and impact of Covid-19 on digital higher education in Germany. *Hum. Behav. Emerg. Tech.* 3, 218–226. doi: 10.1002/hbe2.238
- Zweig, J & Stafford, E. (2016). Training for Online Teachers to Support Student Success: Themes from a Survey Administered to Teachers in Four Online Learning Programs. *Journal of Online Learning Research* (2016) 2(4), 399-418